

WEIGHT LOSS IN MALIGNANCIES

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Abstract

Background: One of the most common causes of weight loss is malignant tumours (especially gastrointestinal, pancreatic, lung, lymphoma, renal and prostate cancers), which often cause weight loss through various mechanisms of this phenomenon [6]. A plethora of current reports state that unintentional weight loss (UWL) may be used as a marker prior to the development of malignant processes. Most studies suggest that the main endogenous sources of energy during weight loss progression in cancer are primarily triglycerides in adipose tissue and skeletal muscle protein [3].

Conclusions: We can report with certainty that weight loss is an important prognostic factor in cancer; the greater the degree of weight loss, the shorter the survival time. The prognostic effect of weight loss is greater in patients with a better prognosis. The aim of this literature review was to explain the pathogenetic chains involved in involuntary weight loss in malignant processes with the development of cancer cachexia, also reporting clinical signs and complications of these.

Keywords: cancer, body weight, weight loss, cancer cachexia.

Introduction

Weight loss (WL) or underweight is defined as an involuntary reduction in normal body weight of more than 5% for 1 month or 10% for 6 months [1]. Cancer cachexia describes a syndrome of progressive weight loss, anorexia and persistent erosion of host body cell mass in response to malignant growth. Although often associated with preterminal patients carrying disseminated disease, cachexia may be present in the early stages of tumor growth before any signs or symptoms of malignancy.

Epidemiologically, anorexia and weight loss are present in 15 to 40% of all cancer patients at diagnosis, but the prevalence appears to be higher in those diagnosed with lung cancer (60%) or upper gastrointestinal cancer (80%) [11].

From the pathogenetic aspect, cytokines, inflammatory process and hypermetabolic state develop as a result of increased resting energy consumption (also called basal metabolic rate), measured by indirect calorimetry and observed in patients with lung cancer, haematological diseases and sarcomas, being considered as

one of the causes of weight loss observed in cancer cachexia. A large number of observations indicate that cytokines, polypeptides released mainly by immune cells, are responsible for some of the metabolic disturbances associated with the hypermetabolic state that partly characterises cachexia in cancer. Due to the growth capacity of BMR and the induction of anorexia tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), IL-1 β and IL-6 have been regarded as plausible mediators of cancer cachexia. Some studies have detected increased concentrations of cytokines in peripheral blood mononuclear cells, especially TNF- α and IL-6, among patients with cancer cachexia [12]. The possible role of cytokines in several types of cancer has been demonstrated in the following studies:

A study of 87 patients with non-small cell lung cancer found that 26 had lost more than 10% of their pre-illness weight. Patients with weight loss manifested a significantly greater systemic inflammatory response, characterized by increased plasma concentrations of soluble TNF receptor, IL-6, CRP, and other adhesion molecules[12]

Pic.1 Mechanisms involved in cancer cachexia[2].

The picture above shows that several factors are involved in cancer cachexia. Tumour-derived catabolic factors, such as pro-inflammatory cytokines, act on target tissues to cause excessive catabolism. Central nervous system damage reduces food intake and increases catabolic neuronal production. Proteolysis is induced in skeletal and cardiac muscle by regulation of the ubiquitin-proteasome system and autophagy. Reduced protein synthesis has also been reported. Loss of adipose tissue results from increased lipolysis, decreased lipogenesis and adipogenesis and browning of white adipose tissue [2].

TWEAK (TNF-related weak inducer of apoptosis) is a cytokine that is related to the TNF/TNFR superfamily. In preclinical work, its receptor, Fn14 (also called TWEAKR), when expressed in malignant disease, appears to be associated with the development of cachexia. Moreover, antibodies targeting Fn14 appear to improve survival in animal models by preventing loss of fat and muscle without any evidence of an antineoplastic effect [2]. Further evidence in support of the hypothesis that TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 serve as mediators in cancer cachexia comes from animal studies: administration of any of these cytokines to laboratory animals induces cachexia. Proinflammatory cytokines such as the IL-6 superfamily, TNF- α , IL-1 and others cause anorexia, lipolysis and muscle breakdown when injected systemically [13,18]. One study evaluated 50 patients: 24 with cancer, 10 with Alzheimer's disease and weight loss, 9 with Alzheimer's disease without weight loss, and 7 healthy individuals. Using an assay for lipid mobilization involving incubation of human serum or urine with murine adipocytes and subsequent measurement of glycerol release from the adipocytes, these researchers found that cancer patients demonstrated significantly higher rates of lipid mobilization compared to other patient groups. Activation of the adenosine triphosphate (ATP)-ubiquitin-proteasome pathway may play an important role in cancer-associated tissue loss, as illustrated by the following observations [13]:

Rats bearing the Yoshida AH-130 ascitic hepatoma exhibit notable muscle loss after tumor implantation, including a 30% loss of gastrocnemius and extensor digitorum longus muscle mass. On day 7 after tumor implantation, free ubiquitin and ubiquitin conjugates were higher in gastrocnemius muscle of tumor-implanted rats than in muscle from control rats [13]. There was also an increase in ubiquitin messenger RNA levels in skeletal muscle of tumor-bearing animals compared to control animals. Several proinflammatory cytokines, including TNF and IL-1, stimulate ubiquitin messenger RNA production. In an animal model of cancer cachexia, inhibition of the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway with the proteasome inhibitor MG132 attenuated weight loss [13]. Thus, the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway may be the final common pathway that mediates protein degradation in cachexia [4].

Another pathway involved in the weight loss mechanism is the JAK/STAT pathway. Janus kinases (JAKs) are a family of kinases that include JAK1, JAK2, JAK3 and tyrosine kinase 2 (TYK2); JAKs mediate cytokine signaling by activating signal transducer

and activator of transcription (STAT) levels. The JAK/STAT pathway is activated in a variety of disease states including solid tumors and has also been implicated in cancer-induced muscle wasting [7].

Reduced food intake or absorption also has an impact on WL. Poor oral intake contributes to the energy deficiencies seen in cancer cachexia. Changes in taste and smell as a consequence of chemotherapy may contribute to loss of appetite [5].

A number of non-specific factors associated with cancer can contribute to decreased nutrient intake or absorption. These include decreased food intake due to dysphagia, abdominal pain or distention; early satiety due to enlarged spleen or liver, an abdominal mass or abdominal distention from ascites; decreased gastrointestinal motility and malabsorption resulting from tumour invasion of the gastrointestinal tract (especially the pancreas) or intestinal resection [5].

Malignancies evolve clinically with symptoms that can affect appetite and caloric intake, called secondary or impact symptoms on nutrition, may be related to the underlying disease or the consequence of cachexia. In particular, pain, fatigue, xerostomia, nausea, constipation and depression are common in patients with advanced cancer and can lead to decreased caloric intake if not treated appropriately [2,5].

Looking at the early diagnosis of WL in malignancies, a study was conducted with the aim of identifying biomarkers that reveal the presence of cachexia as early as possible, even before the observation of visible weight loss. Analyses were applied to the Colon-26 (C26) murine model of cachexia. Tumor-bearing mice (n=5) were sacrificed once every 2 days for 14 days, and control mice (n=5) were sacrificed every 4th day. The diseased mice significantly decreased in weight and lost much of their shin muscles by day 9. They lost quadriceps and gastrocnemius muscles by day 7. The earliest markers were found to be decreases in 12 amino acids, occurring on days 4-14, among which methionine decreased first, followed by asparagine, threonine, proline and aspartate [7].

Increased levels of C-reactive protein and other pro-inflammatory markers, as well as decreased levels of albumin, and serum hemoglobin were also observed in 2/3 of the 7716 subjects in the study population. Lower survival rates were also identified in those with high levels of C-reactive protein in advanced stages of cancer [7].

Complications of malignant cachexia include disturbances of bowel function and absorption caused by alterations in the gut microbiome. Cardiac cachexia may also occur as a consequence of loss of cardiac proteins. Cardiac exhaustion also occurs secondary to anticancer, cardiotoxic therapy or the presence of tumours which, by producing certain mediators, favour cardiomyocyte atrophy, with a negative impact on the contractility of the heart. Patients suffering from diaphragm and/or heart cachexia die prematurely due to respiratory and/or heart failure. Cancer survivors have been shown to have an increased risk of developing cardiac complications, which can manifest themselves even years after cancer treatment [8].

Conclusion: In recent years, various studies have been conducted to understand the mechanisms of fat and skeletal muscle loss in cancer cachexia, but these are only now beginning to be translated into clinical therapy. In the near future, new agents will be developed against the many signalling pathways that are important in adipose tissue and skeletal muscle atrophy. It is important to study in more detail and to know the mechanisms involved in order to be able to prevent the appearance of malignant processes, to treat adequately and effectively and to change the prognosis towards a better one, increasing the duration and quality of life of patients.

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